

CURRENT ISSUES IN TRANSLATION STUDIES: CONTEMPORARY TRENDS AND RESEARCH

Student: Baxromjonova Shahlo Baxtiyor qizi
Scientific supervisor: Khamzaev Sobir Amirovich

(PhD, Associate Professor)

Uzbekistan State University of World Languages
Faculty of Foreign Language and Literature, 1 Faculty

Third-year student, group 2331

Shahlobahramjanova38@gmail.com

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada tarjima tadqiqotlari sohasidagi dolzarb masalalarni ko'rib chiqiladi. Unda sun'iy intellekt, globallashuv, yangi texnologiyalarga bo'lgan talab va ularni joriy etish hamda madaniyatlararo aloqalarning kuchayishi tarjimonlarning kasbiy rolini qanday qayta shakllantirgani tahlil qilinadi. Bundan tashqari, maqolada tarjimonlarning turli sohalaridagi madaniyatlararo moslashuvchanligi, kompetentsiyasi va terminologiya bo'yicha bilimlari hamda ularga tegishli bo'lishi kerak bo'lgan fazilatlarni alohida ta'kidlaydi. Shuningdek, unda zamonaviy tadqiqotlarning asosiy jihatlari, jumladan mashina va badiiy tarjima, lokalizatsiya, tahrir jarayonida insonning ishtiroki va o'рни hamda zamonaviy gibrid tarjima yondashuvi ko'rib chiqilgan. Bundan tashqari, maqolada zamonaviy tarjima amaliyotida fanlararo yondashuvning muhim ahamiyatini ta'kidlanadi. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, tarjima nafaqat til bilimlari va tilshunoslikka oid faoliyatlardan iborat, balki kommunikatsiya, madaniyat va texnologiyani birlashtiruvchi ko'p tarmoqli jarayon va ongdir.

Kalit so'zlar: Tarjimon, tarjima tadqiqotlari, sun'iy intellekt, texnologiyalar, globallashuv va lokalizatsiya, madaniyatlararo muloqot, mashina tarjimasi, tarjima texnologiyasi, tarjimonning roli, fanlararo yondashuv, moslashuvchanlik, tendentsiyalar

Аннотация : В данной статье рассматриваются актуальные вопросы в области переводоведения. Анализируется, как искусственный интеллект, глобализация, спрос на новые технологии и их внедрение, а также расширение межкультурного взаимодействия изменили профессиональную роль переводчиков. Кроме того, в исследовании подчеркивается важность межкультурной адаптивности, компетентности и знания терминологии в различных областях, а также качеств, которыми должны обладать переводчики. В ней также рассматриваются ключевые аспекты современных исследований, включая машинный и литературный перевод, локализацию, человеческую постредакцию и современный гибридный подход к переводу. Кроме того, в исследовании подчеркивается важная роль междисциплинарности в

современной переводческой практике. Результаты показывают, что перевод — это не только знание языков и лингвистическая деятельность, но и междисциплинарный процесс и осознание, объединяющее коммуникацию, культуру и технологии.

Ключевые слова: *Переводчик, переводоведение, искусственный интеллект, технологии, глобализация и локализация, межкультурная коммуникация, машинный перевод, переводческие технологии, роль переводчика, междисциплинарный подход, адаптивность, тенденции*

Abstract: *This article addresses current issues in the field of translation studies. It analyses how artificial intelligence, globalisation, the demand for and implementation of new technologies, and increased intercultural interactions have reshaped the professional role of translators. Moreover, the study emphasises intercultural adaptability, competence, and knowledge of terminology in various fields among translators, as well as the qualities they should possess. It also covers key aspects of contemporary research, including machine and literary translation, localisation, human post-editing, and the modern hybrid translation approach. In addition, the study also highlights the crucial role of interdisciplinarity in modern translation practice. The results show that translation is not only about language knowledge and linguistics-related activities, but also a multidisciplinary process and awareness that integrates communication, culture and technology.*

Key words: *Translator, translation studies, artificial intelligence, technologies, globalisation and localisation, intercultural communication, machine translation, translation technology, translator's role, interdisciplinary approach, adaptability, trends.*

In the 21st century, translation studies has become one of the most significant fields in the world. One of the most dominant trends is the growing integration of technology and translation, including the use of computer-assisted translation (CAT) tools, machine translation (MT), and artificial intelligence (AI). With the growth of technology usage, globalisation, and the emergence of artificial intelligence, which has become an integral part of society, the role of translators has changed both in practice and in theory. All these innovations have expanded the scope of translation studies and redefined the role of translators, making it more interdisciplinary and technology-oriented. Translation is now seen not only as a science and an activity related to language, but also as a process that combines language, technology and culture. As Susan Bassnett [1] notes, translation studies has gone beyond purely linguistic equivalence and now encompasses broader social, cultural and technological aspects. In addition, she argues that today's translator must act as an 'intercultural communicator' rather than simply a linguistic mediator.

Furthermore, translators must respect and understand the cultures of other nations. Translation involves not only translating rendering words, but also interpreting them correctly depending on the culture and context in which they are used. Translators must be resourceful and able to adapt to different situations. Furthermore, Akbarova S. [2] mentions that “At the same time, globalization is creating a need for greater cultural sensitivity. A translator cannot afford to overlook cultural issues when translating if the meaning is to be retained rather than getting misrepresented”. This observation is accurate, since without taking cultural characteristics into account, a translation can distort its meaning if the translator simply translates the words. It is necessary to take all these nuances into account and then convey the words while preserving their meaning, taking into account cultural diversity. For example, idioms, jokes or symbols may be perceived differently in another culture if all words are translated literally. For example, the English idiom «break a leg» which means «good luck» cannot be translated literally into many languages, as it would sound strange or even offensive. If cultural aspects are ignored, the text may be misinterpreted and may even offend readers from other cultures.

Moreover, artificial intelligence and technology also play a significant role in translation studies today. Although they can have negative effects, they still bring benefits such as helping translators identify complex terminology, making their work easier, and even correcting their mistakes. Translators now also have the opportunity to use advanced technologies for translation. Stephen Doherty [3] also expressed this opinion in his article: “I contend that the ongoing technological evolution in translation has yielded unprecedented gains in terms of increased translator productivity and consistency, greater global language coverage, and greater support for improving international communication and distribution”

However, as already mentioned, they also have disadvantages, as their implementation requires awareness and the ability to understand new technologies and their use for translators. Furthermore, there are growing concerns that automation could reduce the demand for human translators.

Over the past 2-3 years, it has become difficult to imagine life without AI, as it has already evolved into many industries, and translation studies are no exception. Neural networks, combined with machine translation, have become more efficient and natural. Though they have become the main assistants to translators, as they complement each other and work together to achieve the best accuracy and effect.

Machine translation has become an indispensable part of translation studies. It has become highly sought after and widely used throughout the world in the field of translation. MT translates words from one language to another using computer algorithms. There are now many translation systems available, such as Google Translate, DeepL and ChatGPT, which people use every day all over the world.

According to Stephen Doherty [4], MT uses complex statistical algorithms to analyse large amounts of data in order to create a monolingual language model for each of the two specified languages. The decoder then uses these models to extrapolate the probability of translating a given word or phrase from one language to another, where the most probable co-occurrences of words or phrases are selected as the best translation.

However, they are not perfect, as they may not have sufficient information about linguistics and may be dependent on their own data systems. Thus, any new phrases or terms may be translated incorrectly. The main problem is also that machine translation translates sentences literally and in a straightforward manner. Since language is not just words but also a set of metaphors, idioms, and emotions, computers have trouble understanding them. Therefore, they cannot completely replace translators who know how to distinguish metaphors from literal statements. Real emotions also play an important role, which machines naturally cannot produce, unlike translators. As mentioned, culture is also considered significant, so translators must also be able to understand different cultural differences and apply their knowledge in practice. Although MT is faster and more comprehensive, it still cannot replace real translators, so they work together and collaborate to produce hybrid translations.

As AI and MT became widespread and frequently used, there was a need for human intervention, known as human post-editing. The process involves a human checking and correcting errors of the final results of MT to ensure that they meet standards of fluency, style and accuracy. In this way, it combines the speed of machine translation with the guarantee of accuracy and quality verified by human experience. Machine translation systems often cannot interpret context. For example, the English word 'bank' can mean both a financial institution and the river shore. MT systems may choose the wrong meaning if the context is unclear. Therefore, human post-editing is necessary to ensure accuracy and coherence.

Group of 3 researchers [5] said: "Even if MT can aid the translation process, we must not forget that machine translators are not yet capable of matching the quality of human translations, to which post-editing is becoming a new stage in the translation process". They also emphasise the importance of human intervention and that it is always advisable to do post-editing after machine translation.

Moreover, in today's world, globalization and localisation have become two interrelated and central concepts in translation studies. Globalisation is the growing interconnection between cultures, countries and markets through the exchange of ideas and information. Thus, it means creating content that will be understood by audiences around the world. Localisation, on the other hand, focuses on adapting content to the cultural, linguistic and social norms of a specific audience. It is not limited to language

alone, but also changes symbols, currencies, or even strategies so that they are perceived as ‘local’.

Furthermore in a rapidly changing world and with innovations in the field of translation studies, translators must be adaptable and apply an interdisciplinary approach. Translation is linked to other fields such as psychology, culture, technology and even marketing. Modern translators must understand the subjects and terminology of various disciplines, including adaptability and understanding of new technologies and changing professional requirements. Thus, all these innovations require translators to constantly update their skills and knowledge, as well as integrate technological knowledge into their practice.

In conclusion, it can be said that modern translation studies combine language, culture and technology. The integration of artificial intelligence, machine translation and globalisation has changed the role of the translator, making it interdisciplinary. Although technologies such as AI and MT increase the speed and efficiency of translation, they can still make mistakes and fail to understand cultural contexts or idioms, so they require human intervention and post-editing. Therefore, translators in today's world must be able to adapt, develop intercultural competence and learn new skills.

REFERENCES:

1. Bassnet.S. (2014). Translation studies (3 ed.) London and New York: Routledge [1,13]
2. Akbarova S. current issues of translation studies [2,144]
3. Stephen Doherty, the impact of translation technologies on the process and Product of translation (International journal of communication 10) [3,950]
4. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/323993653_Human_Post-editing_in_Hybrid_Machine_Translation_Systems_Automatic_and_Manual_Analysis_and_Evaluation